

COMPARISON OF THE EDUCATION SYSTEM OF UZBEKISTAN, CHINA AND SOUTH KOREA

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Abstract. This following article gives us detailed information about the education systems in Uzbekistan, China, and South Korea. In this article, we will mainly explore school education, academic performance and educational work that is carried out in these countries. There will be detailed descriptions of how classes are conducted, intermediate tests, entrance exams, as well as the personal attitude of the people to education. We will give information about school holidays and weekdays.

Keywords: education system, Uzbekistan, China, South Korea, school, university, assessment system, final exams, student.

The education system is a set of educational institutions designed to introduce education into society, to provide intelligentsia. Education in every culture is understood differently, but the goal of all educational institutions is the same - knowledge. In all countries, people pay special attention to training and education, all the presidents of the world, in order to ensure a good future for their people, are trying in every possible way to improve their education system.

Uzbekistan

In Uzbekistan, the direct management of the activities of educational institutions is carried out by two sectoral ministries - the Ministry of Public Education (MPE) and the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education (MHSSE).

The MPE is responsible for the activities of pre-school, out-of-school educational institutions and general education schools. The MPE is responsible for universities and 16 institutes for advanced training of teachers. The Ministry has regional, district and city departments of public education, which carry out the functions of methodological management of the activities of the relevant educational institutions in the territory under their jurisdiction. With the coming to power of Sh. Mirziyoyev, great changes took place in the field of education. Schools switched to a 11-year system of education at the request of the general public. Education in grades 10 and 11 of high school is not mandatory: after grade 9, the student has the right to choose to study in secondary specialized institutions or continue education in high school.

MHSSE is a government body that manages higher and secondary specialized, vocational education in the republic. The Ministry in its activities is accountable to the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The system of the Ministry includes the Center for Secondary Specialized Vocational Education, the Center for the Development of Higher and Secondary Specialized Vocational Education, and subordinate higher educational institutions.

In Uzbekistan, there are 4 stages of education:

1. Preschool education
2. General secondary education (compulsory)
3. Secondary special education (professional)
4. Higher education

Preschool education

The main task of kindergarten is to prepare children for school.

In pre-school education, children are admitted to kindergartens from the age of two and study until the age of 7. In kindergartens, children are being prepared for school. They spend the whole day there as their parents bring them in the morning by 8:00 and pick them up only in the evening. Children are fed there three times a day and in between have fruit snacks. The menu for kindergartens is prepared by a nurse who also monitors the health of each child and in accordance with this, can prohibit or allow any dishes or exercises. In kindergartens, in addition to teachers, there are also technicians who monitor the order of the group given to them. In Uzbek kindergartens, there are no special holidays. Mostly children are given a rest for several days on holidays. But it is worth noting that children do not go to kindergartens on Saturdays and Sundays so they are trained based on a five-day system.

School education

School education in Uzbekistan is carefully controlled by the Ministry of Public Education, as it is compulsory.

Children are accepted in school from the age of 7 and are educated. Schools in Uzbekistan are divided into:

- Primary education (grade 1 to grade 4)
- Secondary compulsory education (from grade 5 to grade 9)

And education from grade 10 to grade 11, if after grade 9 the student did not leave and did not enter a secondary special educational institution.

Here, children study for 11 years, study begins in September and lasts until May, there are 4 quarters in each academic year and the school timing is divided into two parts (airway: from eight in the morning to twelve in the afternoon or second: from one in the afternoon to six in the evening). In Uzbek schools, children are assessed on a five-point scale and grades are placed on the digital educational platform "Kundalik". There is no unified school uniform in the country: the Government of Uzbekistan, by a decree dated October 3, 2022, abolished the obligation to wear a unified school uniform in public schools.

Primary School

Children are accepted to school at the age of 7, immediately after the end of kindergarten. For admission into the school, they prepare the necessary documents and go through an interview, which is the last stage of selection in the school. In elementary school, children study from grade 1 to grade 4. During this time they learn to write and read, as well as learning grammar. The main lessons in the lower grades are taught by one teacher, and only secondary lessons are taught by different teachers.

Secondary school

Secondary school starts in the 5th grade and continues through the 9th. Each academic year is divided into 4 parts:

- First quarter from September to November
- Second quarter from November to December
- Third quarter from January to March
- Fourth quarter from March to May.

In these classes, children are prepared in various subjects and are prepared to enter higher educational institutes. With each class, the level of difficulty increases, new lessons are added to

the old lessons and some subjects are completely replaced by others. According to the Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 696 of November 19, 2021, the “Regulation on the procedure for calculating the average indicator of grades of graduates of educational institutions and its accounting for university entrance exams” was approved. Grades from grade 6 of compulsory secondary education to 11 years of study will be taken into account in state examinations. Also, after the 9th grade, students have the right to go to secondary specialized educational institutes, where they can continue their studies in their chosen specialty. And if they stay for the 10th grade, then they will continue their education in the school system and will prepare for state exams. State exams are very important for applicants, they prepare for these exams throughout the high school. State exams take place before the start of the new academic year after school exams, which take place at the end of May, and state exams in August. Examinations are held for a whole month and are conducted by Davlat Test Markazi (State Testing Center) abbreviated as DTM. During this month, exams are held for all specialties and for all universities. The points scored are announced every other day and can be found on the DTM official website or through special Telegram bots.

There are two types of holidays in the Uzbek education system:

- Half term holidays between terms. The duration of such holidays is not large: from one week to three weeks.
- Summer holidays are 100 days long. These holidays begin on March 25 before the start of the new school day.

But despite such a huge vacation period, teachers do not leave their students without any additional tasks for the holidays.

China

China is definitely one of the leading countries where education is highly valued by the people. Since childhood, the Chinese have been working, going to school, getting higher education and getting a job. But their journey does not end there. In one of the Beijing 2021 articles, according to statistics, the number of people who received or are receiving higher education reached 218.36 million and their share in the total population of the country increased from 8,930 per 100,000 people in 2010 to 15,467 per 100 thousand people in 2020. In addition, according to the census article, the illiteracy rate among the Chinese population has dropped to 2.67 percent (which was several times higher in the 1990s). All these figures are proof that the Chinese are working hard, because in the 90s, only 4% of the population had a higher education, 12% had a high school diploma and 11% of the population had no education. This was the reason and further impetus for the radical change. Now, the people of China cannot imagine their life without a diploma because a diploma for them is the fruit of a happy and stable life. It is because of this that parents, desiring happiness for their child, fully invest all their efforts in the education of the child, and it all starts from school.

China's education system is very similar to the European education system:

- From 3 to 6 years old children receive preschool education in kindergartens
- From 6 to 12 years the child receives knowledge in primary school (6 years)
- Next 3 years are high school
- Last 3 years of study - high school

Total 12 years of study (12 grades). Holidays for Chinese students is considered happiness. During the year, students go on vacation twice:

- Summer holidays (beginning of July - September)

- Winter (New Year's) holidays - mid-January to mid-February.

Preschool education

As in all countries, children attend kindergarten to prepare the child for school. Schools in China are private and public. It is from a young age that the children are taught responsibilities and are introduced to love for hard work as the well-known feature of Chinese discipline requires this from early childhood.

School education

As in all schools in the world, there are 3 levels of school education:

- Primary
- Secondary
- Higher education

In China, the first 9 years of education (primary and secondary school) are compulsory and free.

In elementary school, children learn the Chinese language, science, mathematics, music, natural history, and ethics. Subjects are gradually added such as geography, botany, etc. . Students are assessed on a 100-point scale. It is in secondary school that students study the exact sciences, languages and humanities in depth. After middle school, students do not have to go to high school. Students can apply to a technical school or college to receive a secondary professional education. Why did the Chinese go to such extremes? Because high school in China is paid. That is, students who are going to enter higher institutes study in high school, where they are prepared for entering a university. Before starting high school, students take a profile test and choose their direction - vocational or academic. What is the difference?

- Academic high school prepares students for university entrance
- Vocational High School aims to train future employees

General information

- In China, there is a test method of assessment at each transitional stage.
- There is a single unified school uniform for all Chinese schools.
- Every day, students have 6-7 lessons (in high school, 8-9). Following this, students spend their whole day at school.

- Lessons last 40 minutes.
- Physical education lessons are held every day.

South Korea

South Korea is famous for its strong education system. We have heard more than once that in South Korea there is very strong competition from school, continuing with tutors and ending with job search. Only smart and able students can get a job in the most popular and prestigious companies. The introduction to children that education is an important aspect of a child's life and future happiness from adults, is still practiced in modern Korean society. Parents do not regret money spent for the education of their child, from kindergarten to higher education, because they know that a good education in prestigious universities is a direct path to a stable and well-paid job. This system has become the culture of the South Korean people.

The structure of the education system in South Korea is:

- from 3 to 6 years of pre-school education (kindergarten)
- from 6 to 12 years old - primary school
- next 3 years - high school

- 3 years - high school
- University

The academic year is divided into semesters:

- 1st semester: from the beginning of March to mid-July
- 2nd semester: from the end of August to mid-February

Preschool education

Pre-school education is not mandatory, but many parents enroll their children in kindergartens. There are several reasons for this:

- Due to parents who are busy all day at work
- For the comprehensive development of children
- Preparing the child for elementary school

Preschool education is also divided into stages:

- 나리반 [nariban] - a nursery for children from 3 days to 3 years old
- 어린집 [orinchib] - middle groups from 2 to 6 years old
- 유치원 [yuchiwon] - older groups for preparation for school, where children are from 4 to 6 years old

Kindergartens in South Korea are paid and not cheap at all. For low-income families, the state helps with various benefits and allocation of the state budget. In addition, kindergartens are open 5 days a week from 8.30 to 14.00. But there are also private kindergartens that look after the child during the day. In elementary grades, students go in no uniform, but in private schools uniform is required.

School education

Primary grades (초등학교)

Primary grades includes the first 6 years of study (6 grades). Primary and secondary school are compulsory. In elementary grades, subjects such as mathematics, Korean, music, social sciences, English, and art are studied. As in Uzbekistan, the main subjects (Korean, mathematics, drawing, social sciences) are taught by the class teacher themselves. Classes in elementary school usually start at 9:00 am and continue until 16:00.

Secondary School (중학교)

In the secondary school, education continues for children from 13 to 16 years old (from grades 7 to 9). Children are getting older. In addition, the number of new subjects (Chinese characters (한자), economics, history, literature, etc.) and lesson hours is also increasing. All students' lessons are held in the same class: each grade has its own timetable with the class number and its own class where all the lessons are held. Teachers themselves come to the class room according to the schedule. The only exceptions are those school subjects where you need to work outside the classroom or in laboratories. Usually, every day in high school there are 6 lessons. Lessons at the secondary school start at 8:00 am and continue until 15:30. After 6 lessons, students attend clubs, sports sections or take lessons from private tutors.

High School (고등학교)

The next 3 years of study (from 16 to 19 years). These years are very difficult for each student as the workload increases, the number of lessons per day exceeds 10 hours, additional

classes with tutors. Lessons in high school, as well as in secondary school, begin at 8.00 am and end at 15:30. After the end of the lessons, students attend sports practices and clubs as for receiving awards in any competitions or Olympiads, students receive special grants for admission to the university. In fact, high school is not compulsory to attend, since, as in China, students can apply for admission to technical schools in order to receive secondary special education, however, almost all, exactly 98% of all students, graduate from high school. This figure is the highest on the planet. The main goal of the high school is to prepare high school students to pass the final exams 수능 [suneun]. The final 수능 (SCAT) exam includes 3 compulsory disciplines: mathematics, Korean and English. Passing the suneun is considered one of the most important events in the life of any Korean since admission to university depends on the test result. According to the final score obtained, students get the opportunity to enter a certain university to which they applied: the higher the score, the greater the chances of getting into the university that the student has chosen. South Korea is preparing for this day meticulously: air travel over South Korea is suspended on the day of the exam so that for 35 minutes while students are taking listening, no one and nothing distracts them. In case a student gets lost, forgets documents at home or is late, the government has allocated special patrols that will make sure that each student gets to the exam on time. Public transport (trains and buses) starts working earlier so that everyone has time to get to the exam venue.

General information

- As in Uzbekistan, students are admitted to public schools based on registration/place of residence. Also, private schools are famous in Korea where there is a lot of competition.
- The buildings of Primary, middle and high schools have different locations (representatives of these schools do not study in the same building)
- Pupils after each intermediate testing are determined by places (Rating). After the end of testing, the rating of all students, including parallel classes, is displayed on the school bulletin board.
- Some students in Korea do not have time to make permanent friendships, because every year, randomly, students are assigned to different classes.
 - All lessons are 45 minutes long.
 - Education in Korea is free.
 - Each school has its own name.
 - Grades do not affect the transition from class to class. The most important stage in school life is the entrance exams.
 - Korea has a testing system.
 - Each school has its own uniform, which can be purchased at district stores linked to the school.
 - School meals are free.

Table of differences between the educational systems of Uzbekistan from China and South Korea:

Uzbekistan	China	South Korea
<p>1. The school has 2 shifts: 1st shift - 8.00 am, 2nd shift - 13.00 pm</p> <p>2. Primary school is 4 years old</p> <p>3. The period of study from elementary to high school lasts 11 years</p> <p>4. Holidays between each quarter of study: autumn, winter, spring and summer holidays</p> <p>5. Beginning of the school year from September</p> <p>6. Free education</p> <p>7. Introduction to subjects such as botany, geography, history, etc. , takes place in high school (from grade 5)</p> <p>8. Evaluation of children takes place on a five-point scale</p> <p>9. A terrible school has 1 direction - preparing students for admission to the university</p> <p>10. For admission to the university, all students take exams at the DTM (State Testing Center)</p> <p>11. The system of a single school uniform. Rule "white top, black bottom"</p>	<p>1. There is only one shift</p> <p>2. Primary school is 6 years old</p> <p>3. The period of study from elementary to high school lasts 12 years</p> <p>4. Children go on vacation twice a year</p> <p>5. Beginning of the school year in September</p> <p>6. High school is paid</p> <p>7. Gradual introduction of these subjects in primary school</p> <p>8. Evaluation of students on a hundred-point scale</p> <p>9. 2 directions in high school (academic and specialized technical)</p> <p>10. Chinese graduates take exams, and their admission to universities depends on the scores of these exams.</p> <p>11. The system of a single school uniform. In large cities, black, green or blue bottoms and white tops were especially popular: dresses with blouses for girls and trousers with shirts for boys. With the introduction of a single standard for urban schools in 1993, the tracksuit became the main trend in school fashion for the next 22 years.</p>	<p>1. There is only one shift</p> <p>2. Primary school is 6 years old</p> <p>3. The period of study from elementary to high school lasts 12 years</p> <p>4. Children go on vacation twice a year</p> <p>5. Beginning of the academic year from August</p> <p>6. Free education</p> <p>7. Phased introduction of these subjects in primary school</p> <p>8. Evaluation of students on a hundred-point scale</p> <p>9. 1 direction (preparation for passing the final tests (SCAT) for admission to the university)</p> <p>10. To enter the university, students take the SCAT final exams</p> <p>11. The system of a single school uniform. Each school has its own uniform.</p> <p>12. In any school - it doesn't matter if it is private or public - physical education is held at least three times a week.</p> <p>13. The system of rating students by grades</p> <p>14. Work of kindergartens from 8.30 to 14.00 in the afternoon</p>

<p>12. Physical education lessons are held 2 times a week and continue throughout the entire 11 years of study</p> <p>13. There is no rating system for grades for the semester of study among peers.</p> <p>14. The work of the children's gardens starts from 8.00 am to 18.00 pm.</p> <p>15. Starting from high school, students begin to go to the classroom of those teachers in the subject they teach (room mode)</p> <p>16. Class naming system: year of study number and alphabetical letter, depending on the number of classes in one year of study (for example: 1 "A", 7 "B", 10 "D")</p>	<p>12. Daily physical education lessons during 12 years of study</p> <p>13. There is a rating system based on grades for the semester of study.</p> <p>14. The work of kindergartens starts from 8.00 am to 18.00 pm.</p> <p>15. All lessons are held in 1 classroom, which is given to a certain class (the only exception is those subjects where you need to work outside the classroom or laboratories)</p> <p>16. Class naming system: the number of the year of study (separately primary, secondary and terrible schools) and the class number according to the number of classes of one year of study (for example: terrible and secondary schools - 1-1, 2-3, 1-3)</p>	<p>15. All lessons are held in 1 classroom, which is given to a certain class (the only exception is those subjects where you need to work outside the classroom or laboratories)</p> <p>16. Class naming system: the number of the year of study (separately primary, secondary and terrible schools) and the class number according to the number of classes of one year of study (for example: terrible and secondary schools - 1-1, 2-3, 1-3)</p>
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Conclusion

What could be added to the education system of Uzbekistan?

Undoubtedly, each education system is unique, each has its pros and cons. The education system of Uzbekistan is constantly changing and improving. Now Uzbekistan is striving to solve its "problems" by bringing the Finnish education system to perfection. But what points of the education system from the above listed countries could be taken to improve the level of education? Undoubtedly, the education system of China and South Korea is very strong and education in these countries is highly valued, which tells us that we have a lot to learn from them.

- In China and South Korea, teachers are highly valued. Their status in society has always been high. Many want to become teachers, because the work of a teacher is valued and well paid by the state.

- Ratings at the end of the semester / quarter. If the ratings of students from certain classes are added to the education system, then there will be a chance of competition. Competition is one of the best ways to strive for excellence.

- Remove the two-shift mode of training. It will be more effective if the schedule and time of the child is correctly distributed on the school day. Such a schedule also requires a free lunch at school, which is not yet available in all schools in Uzbekistan.

- The safety of children always comes first. The most inconvenient in the schools of Uzbekistan - 1 building for kindergartens, primary, secondary schools. Despite the fact that the entire floor of the school building is allocated for primary classes, the canteen, library or similar places are common to all students of the school. Primary school kids are facing high school and middle school students which leads to some frustrating and uncomfortable situations. For the convenience of primary classes, it is best to provide younger students with a separate building with the necessary classrooms, equipment and a dining room for students.

- Schools need to introduce subjects that prepare children for adulthood.
- Teachers / educators should teach children from childhood that all professions are important. So Uzbekistan would reach heights in all spheres of life and industry of the state.

- Radical distortion of corruption in the education system. Thorough fight with corruption. From childhood, children need to develop the mindset that corruption is a dirty and dishonest job.

Our state is developing every year, carrying out new revolutions in all spheres of life, in particular the field of education. High scores indicate that a country is gradually achieving its goals.

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